

Our Heritage, Our Stories

*Linking and searching Community-Generated Digital Content
to develop the people's national collection*

Reporting Guidelines + Template

*OHOS Community Fund
University of Glasgow*

The OHOS team thanks you warmly for your contributions to OHOS, as a Community Fund recipient. Your feedback contributes to case studies and data collection for White Papers and peer-reviewed journal articles. We would be grateful for all reflections on your activities, with a particular focus on how the activity met with the Eligibility Criteria, below. We would also ask that you anonymise the names of any participants. All of the data used will adhere to GDPR.

1.0 Details of the Community Fund Recipient

Name (s): Lydia Honeybone, Shireen Taylor, Mina Heydari-Waite and Lydia Beilby

Organisation: Offline (trading name of GAMIS, Glasgow Artists' Moving Image Studios)

Partner(s):

Amount received:

Please provide a brief description of the activities undertaken through the Community Fund:

We worked with Govanhill-based artist Mina Heydari-Waite to develop and deliver a collaborative project 'The Ground Is Not Unchanging'. Activities include film screenings, an exhibition, and experimental archiving workshops. We received OHOS funding for the workshop element, which draws from both the screenings and exhibition which will run beforehand.

The two experimental archiving workshops were led by Heydari-Waite and artist-filmmaker, and 16mm specialist, Lydia Beilby.

2.0 Benefits to the Organisation

Please write up to 800 words on how the activity met with your organisation's aims and objectives, with particular reference to improving the content, connectedness and completeness of community archives.

These workshops set out to challenge preconceived ideas of what an archive can be and who holds the authority to shape them. The artists considered what material is held in the community, and explored textual and visual interventions (like erasure, replacement, juxtaposition and association) through the use of storytelling and capturing footage on 16mm film, reanimating a 'living archive'.

Though there was a very practical skills sharing element to these workshops, much of the two-days were spent in discussion, finding points of connection and difference in the participants' lived experiences. How they recapture lost archives, what they take from their personal stories of migration and loss. Then, using the objects (or lack of objects) they brought with them, this was committed to 16mm film to form a collaborative short experimental colour film or new collaborative archive.

Working in this way and with this medium (16mm film) was a new approach for Heydari-Waite and many of the participants so the workshop was both an opportunity for skills sharing and learning new archiving methodologies but also to explore the conceptual opportunities that this and other now defunct video recording mediums offer e.g. Hi8, VHS, Beta, DV tapes, mediums used in Heydari-Waite's work and explored with the group as a material that is degrading to the point of complete loss.

In the first session, participants discussed what this degradation means for the stories of lives captured on this tape and offered up their own objects, telling the stories they hold. They collectively decided how to archive them on 16mm film. The second session was the practical implementation of the plan to document the objects they brought to the sessions.

Finally, we will hold a sharing event where we come together to watch the short film they made. Unfortunately, there is a backlog of film processing at the lab and the participants' film is still not back yet so this event has been postponed.

3.0 Benefits to the Participants

Please write up to 800 words on how the activity benefited the participants. This could include anything from technical skills gained, to confidence in the worth of CGDC/ their own collections.

For example, did the activity produce new resources with strong community significance, or to extending/enhancing such existing content? Perhaps it developed innovative methods of managing content that will substantially benefit community groups (individually or more broadly), or to developing community skills in archival approaches.

We would also be grateful if you could include any feedback from participants, whether recorded verbally during the activity or received after (emails, IG messages, etc).

The focus of the workshop was to collect the almost impossible to capture ephemera of personal archives (some of which have been lost), to tell stories through the objects left behind and build new skills and confidence working with oral histories and technical skills in filming using 16mm film.

Participants benefited from access to and training in 16mm, a medium which requires skilled tuition and is costly to process. This afforded participants space to experiment, granting permission to make mistakes, a luxury not often afforded early career artists or community groups.

It was also clearly beneficial that individuals selected to participate were from a variety of different backgrounds and lived experiences. The task of working with personal ephemera bonded

4.0 Benefits to OHOS

Please write up to 800 words on how the activity met with OHOS aims and objectives.

You should consider the ways in which the activity expanded the diversity of materials, peoples, and stories represented within the UK national collection and showcases the diversity and complexity of our cultural heritage.

You may reflect in how far the activity/outputs:

....foreground historically under-represented communities and histories.

.... challenges existing narratives or practices.

.....Served to connect diverse sets of people and stories.

....enabled people taking part to learn more about CGDC.

... encouraged people taking part to learn about OHOS and how it can support their archive's goals

... enabled people taking part to have new experiences by exploring their collections

... encouraged people taking part to share experience, skills and information about their archives/collections

... encouraged people to reflect and plan re: the sustainability of their online collections.

....foreground historically under-represented communities and histories.

The workshop was led by British-Iranian artist, Mina Heydari-Waite and Scottish artist-filmmaker, Lydia Beilby. The participants were selected to ensure a diverse mix of lived experiences, cultural backgrounds and being local to the geographic area. We advertised the opportunity to participate via open call, worded; “We would particularly like to encourage participants who have experience or histories of migration, and whose stories may feel absent from conventional narratives on Scotland’s history.”

Because of this wording, we received several applications from participants who proposed exploring themes of migration through the workshop, e.g. *“toward the tail end of lockdown, i was hit with two immense, world-/self-shattering events: my unplanned journey into motherhood and my home nation Sudan being flung into war, with no return to homeland in sight.”*

.... challenges existing narratives or practices.

The workshop used participants’ own archival material (object, photographs, film, letters or more intangible things like memories, stories, song lyrics, dreams) which used the artists’ own research methodologies and expertise to work with participants to create a new experimental 16mm moving image work.

.....Served to connect diverse sets of people and stories.

As stated, the group was intentionally composed of diverse participants who learnt from each other’s lived experiences. We created a safe and supportive environment for participants to share their stories, offering travel fees, childcare and lunch provided on each day.

...enabled people taking part to learn more about CGDC.

This group of participants were all local to the host organisation, Offline. Though the workshop discussed analogue filmmaking methodologies, and the final experimental co-created film is on 16mm, this will be scanned and form a digital archive of the project.

... encouraged people taking part to learn about OHOS and how it can support their archive's goals

The participants were previously unaware of the work of OHOS, through this workshop, they had the chance to meet Abi and learn more about the work OHOS do and how they can contribute.

... enabled people taking part to have new experiences by exploring their collections

This was a very intimate workshop that introduced the idea of small personal archives, participants had the chance to learn to think about their own and other participants' objects as archival materials with sociopolitical value beyond the personal.

... encouraged people taking part to share experience, skills and information about their archives/collections

As above.

... encouraged people to reflect and plan re: the sustainability of their online collections.